

FORMATION OF VOLUNTARY QUALITIES IN STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF TEACHINGS OF EASTERN SCHOOLS

Qosimboyeva Gulg'uncha Nuriddin kizi

Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

1st year student of Pedagogy faculty

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10784589>

Annotation: In this article, our scholars such as Alisher Navoi, Abdurrahman Jami, Saadi Shirazi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Unsurulmaoli Kaikovus have provided information about the formation of volitional qualities based on their teachings.

Key words: will, allama, east, teaching, student, maturity, "Makhbub ul-kulub", personality, society.

Introduction:

The thinkers who created in Central Asia in the Middle Ages created an incomparable scientific treasure, their rich creativity, scientific and philosophical thoughts are still important today. Among them, we can mention Abu Nasr Farabi, Ibn Sina, Musa al-Khorezmi and many other scholars. Central Asia has become one of the centers of new philosophical and scientific knowledge in the Islamic world. The great scientists and thinkers who came out of this place make a great contribution to the formation and development of philosophy and science. Most of the works of Eastern scholars contain the necessary knowledge and skills for young people and students. In their scientific heritage, we can find necessary and valuable information about the issues of personality formation, education, and the acquisition of behavioral standards by a person.

Who is Scientist himself? - this word is an Arabic word meaning "learned". A scholar is considered an Islamic honorific title for a person who is well-educated, widely read and knowledgeable, or a great scholar. This name was given by scholars of Islamic jurisprudence and philosophy. It is used as an honorific in both Sunni Islam and Shia Islam, mainly in South Asia, the Middle East, and Iran. In our country, there are many people who have received this great name. In particular, we can cite scholars such as Alisher Navoi, Abdurakhman Jami, Sadi Sheerazi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Raykhan Beruni, Jalaliddin Davani, Unsurulmaoli Kaikovus. They created based on their teachings.

Doctrine is a set of theoretical rules and conclusions, scientific views in a certain field of events in existence, branches of science, social life, society and so on. In their works, many scholars of the East have put forward valuable ideas about the formation of will and volitional qualities and the importance of these qualities in human life.

Will is the ability of a person to control his own activities and mental processes. Will is characterized not by the experience of "I want", but by the experience of "I must", "I want". The will appears and is acquired mainly in work. Most of Alisher Navoi's works focus on education. Especially in one of his most famous works, the valuable work written at the end of his life, "Makhbub ul-kulub", this topic is emphasized. This work is concisely written by the author. The student who reads the work will read it with interest without any difficulty. The work is divided into articles by the author, and each article is marked with a certain number.

Each of these articles has a different theme and covers different topics. This is the main reason for increasing the value of the work. The second part of the work is devoted to the issues of ethics and education. It contains information necessary for young students. A. Navoi encouraged to improve the life of working people, to make ordinary people literate, to enlighten them.

The famous oriental scholar Unsurulmaoli Kaikovus talks about youth in the work "Nightmare". He shows three types of emotions in people: intelligence, truth and youth. He says that three things form the foundation of youth:

- 1. Going over what he said; that is, truth;**
- 2. Not betraying the truth;**
- 3. Keeping a good deed in front.**

According to him, all other human emotions depend on these three things. He considers the pillars of youth to be the following: bravery, courage, patience, keeping one's promises, being honest and clean, and others. According to him, personal qualities are not born, but are formed during life, and he emphasizes that how to form them depends on the will of a person.

Abdurakhman Jami also paid special attention to education in his works. When talking about upbringing, he emphasizes that attention and patience should be paid to everything, and good care is needed. In his opinion, he said that even a pale rose can flourish if it is given attention and care, and a human child can be perfect if it is given proper education. In his works, Farabi emphasizes several human qualities such as patience, endurance, and endurance as the main criterion of spiritual maturity. He said that in order for a person to be spiritually mature, he must be spiritually pure, able to overcome various habits, and know that he can control his will. Abu Raykhan Beruni's scientific views on human life are also very interesting. Alloma stated in his works that the will and volitional qualities are of special importance in the development of a person. He especially emphasized that a person can achieve perfection only if he can control his positive and negative aspects. These works not only increase intellectual and voluntary qualities of students, but also develop their spiritual maturity.

References:

1. Mavlonova. R.A. "General pedagogy". T.- 2018
2. Yakubova. Sh.E. Approaches to the formation of a positive worldview in students. News of UzMU Vestnik NUUz ACTA NUUz PHILOSOPHY 1/5/1 2023
3. B.Kh. Khodjayev Theory and practice of general pedagogy. Textbook. - T.: "Sano-standard" publishing house, 2017, 416 pages.